

Regulating Vehicle Access
for improved Livability

Dynamic kerbside management

Sandboxing project for the City of London

WSP

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Table of Contents

Document history	4
Terminology	5
About the ReVeAL project	6
Introduction.....	6
Background	7
Objective.....	8
<i>Hypothesis</i>	9
Method.....	9
<i>Point of departure</i>	9
<i>Model</i>	11
<i>Assumptions</i>	16
<i>Results</i>	19
Evaluation.....	24
Summary and conclusions.....	26

Summary sheet

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Abstract	The aim of this deliverable is to explore whether/how the City of London can manage its kerbside space more efficiently and improve the city's livability by optimising the traffic having stopping purposes along a street's kerbsides. This is done through a sandboxing model, a virtual environment, where experimentation with the regulation of the street is possible.
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Terminology

Adoption rate – the share of clients/objects that adopts to a new introduced activity in the system such as a sub system of bookable parking spots in a parking system.

First come, first serve – a system where the priority to a limited supply is determined by arrival time, i.e., a normal priority system for on-street parking.

Grade of service – in queuing theory, the grade of service represents the least tolerated service rate. A 30% grade of service means that 30% of the clients in the system will be blocked from the system's service.

Service time – in queuing theory, the time needed to perform a task excluding the time spent queuing. In this case, the time needed at the loading space for a specific vehicle.

About the ReVeAL project

Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVARs) are one of the tools that can help make cities more liveable, healthier and more attractive for all, and help support the achievements of some of their goals for transport. The goal of the EU Horizon 2020 project ReVeAL is to support cities producing good practice in UVAR and to add UVARs to the standard range of urban mobility approaches across Europe and beyond.

The ReVeAL project supports UVAR implementation in six pilot cities – Bielefeld, Helmond, Jerusalem, Padua, City of London, Vitoria Gasteiz - and has developed a toolkit to help other cities decide what UVARs may be appropriate for them and what to be aware of when implementing. To find out more about ReVeAL, please see the [ReVeAL website](#) and the [ReVeAL UVAR decision support tool](#).

Introduction

In the context of the ReVeAL project, kerbside management has been seen as a possible future UVAR – a way to manage and optimise the use of the kerb space. To address the possibility of using kerbside management as a future UVAR an international workshop with leading experts was held in November 2020 (MS18). A report (D3.8) was created based on the workshop and desk research. This has led to this sandboxing exercise (D3.9) with the goal of testing the possibilities of bookable loading bays, here in the context of the City of London.

Kerbside constitutes the boundary between a vehicle and the pedestrian spaces of a city. Regulation of vehicles access to the kerbside can improve pedestrians' perception of the traffic space, and thus, the livability of the city. This sandboxing project is a collaboration between WSP and the City of London and aims at exploring whether the City of London can manage its kerbside space more efficiently and improve the city's livability by optimising the traffic having stopping purposes along a street's kerbsides.

One of the streets having the largest volumes of delivery transports in London is St Mary Axe. St Mary Axe is located at the centre of the City of London and is not part of the arterial transport network or a designated thoroughfare. The buildings located on St Mary Axe are offices and other typical businesses collocated with offices such as cafés and restaurants. Because of its characteristics, St Mary Axe has high volumes of traffic having stopping purposes on the street. This sandboxing project utilises St Mary Axe as a case study. The aim of the sandboxing project described here was to investigate whether different parking systems might have positive effects on the delivery transport by controlling and prioritising the demand to periods of the day where the pedestrian volumes are lower.

The parking is regulated by double yellow road markings on St Mary Axe. Double yellow demarcates that stopping to wait or park is prohibited to some degree, whilst stopping to load/unload and to pick up/set down passengers is generally allowed. On St Mary Axe, a vehicle is allowed to load or unload for a

maximum of 40 minutes¹. Further, on the specific street, there are designated parking spaces for taxis and motorcycles. Loading and unloading take place in underground loading bays or on street.

A regulation of loading and unloading on the street could potentially lead to a more efficient use of the kerbside. A prohibition on stopping outside demarcated areas along the street could result in releasing space for other purposes or limiting the risk of blocking other traffic on the street. The first question is how many parking spaces would be needed to make this kind of regulation successful, without risking delivery failures.

It is also assumed that digitalisation could lead to a more efficient use of a regulated street with demarcated loading zones. This could be done using a remotely accessible booking system via an application in a smartphone, for example. Therefore, the second question is which conditions must be fulfilled for such a system to perform more efficiently (lower risk of delivery failure) than a traditional non-bookable system.

In this report, data including stopping activities on St Mary Axe were used to create a *sandboxing model*, a virtual environment, where experimenting with the regulation of the street will be possible. This includes exploration of the data itself as well as the simulation of two main scenarios:

1. Alternative 1: a parking system constituted of designated loading spaces. Parking is only allowed in the designated loading bays, hence, parking on the street will not be regulated by double yellow.
2. Alternative 2: a parking system constituted of bookable loading spaces together with some additional non-bookable loading bays.

Background

Queuing theory

Queuing theory is a way of studying queues mathematically using statistic characteristics. For example, one could describe a queue to a call centre, using properties like the expected number of calls received within a time period, and the expected duration of each call. Assuming there is a certain number of operators, it will be possible to statistically estimate the average number of callers waiting to be served. In the same way, a street with loading spaces can be described using the arrival frequency and service times.

While traditional loading spaces can be described using simple queuing theory, a booking system is more complex. First, a booking system is not really a queuing system, as there is no actual queue. Instead, the customers make a request and if it is declined, they can either adjust their request or go somewhere else. The fact that the customers do not enter to the queuing system in order of arrival leads to suboptimal use (described below).

Booking systems

¹ City of London. Yellow lines. <https://www.cityoflondon.gov.uk/services/parking/yellow-lines> (retrieved: 221122)

From a practical perspective, a booking system for loading spaces has limits when it comes to efficiency:

- Suboptimal utilisation – The time between two bookings may be too short to meet a third customer's requested service time, leading to vacancies that would not occur in a *first come, first served* system.
- Overestimation of booking time – A customer may book a longer time than needed, leading to underutilisation.
- Low adoption rate – It cannot be expected that all users will be able (or willing) to use the app for example if they only need to stop for a very short time

The risk of suboptimal use applies to all booking systems where the requested service times of some users is longer than the shortest possible length of service. This will always occur when the requested service times vary between users, as is assumed in the case of bookable loading spaces. The risk of overbooking will occur when the uncertainty of the users arrival corresponds to the length of a bookable time slot. When use is free of charge, this risk could be expected to increase. Both conditions are assumed to apply in the case of bookable loading spaces. The risk of a low adoption rate will lead to a lower demand. It could be expected that these users would instead use non-bookable loading spaces if these exist and are available. In other cases, there is a risk that the users would stop in areas not designated for loading.

In real world practice, it is necessary that the operator decide upon the characteristics of the implemented system. This includes:

- Number of bookable spaces
- Number of non-bookable spaces (if any)
- Length of each time slot

All these characteristics will affect the performance of the system and should be considered in a simulation model. Apart from these, some assumptions are also expected to affect the results of a simulation model. These include:

- Adoption rate: The number of customers that will use the booking system
- Additional service time when booking: Extra time occupied due to overbooking
- Demand: Considering both the arrival frequency and the service times

Objective

St Mary Axe in the City of London is experiencing high volumes of delivery transports restricting pedestrians' access to the pavements and the general street space. A UVAR measure such as a bookable loading system might be able to regulate and optimize the deliveries to volumes that stimulate the perception of livability. This sandboxing project aimed at exploring whether different parking systems would regulate the arrivals of deliveries to a certain number of loading spaces, and thus, providing more space for pedestrians.

The objective of the sandboxing activity for St Mary Axe in the City of London was to create a virtual environment, where a system of bookable and non-bookable loading bays can be simulated to identify how certain assumptions, including adoption rate and overestimation of time needed, affect the efficiency of a booking system.

The research questions that constituted the point of departure of this sandboxing and guided the initial thoughts of the creation of the virtual environment were:

- How many loading bays are needed and how many of these should be bookable and non-bookable?
- How many transports need to change their arrival time and by how much?
- What adoption rates are needed for different utilisation levels?

Hypothesis

The virtual environment in this sandboxing project was explored following the hypothesis that it is possible to model a booking system for loading and unloading vehicles using general mathematical methods. General mathematical methods allow us to form a virtual environment that is not heavily dependent on several geographical attributes such as an exact arrival data set or street layout. Hence, if successful, the method would be able to analyse the effects of bookable parking systems at other streets or cities as well.

Method

Point of departure

The City of London provided data describing the stopping activities at St Mary Axe. The data was collected on Wednesday 20th November and Thursday 21st November 2019 by 12 video cameras filming the street's vehicle activity. The data included the information described in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of provided data set.

Attribute	Description
Parking location	Parking location on St Mary Axe.
Date	Date of event
Arrival time	Arrival time on a minute basis.
Departure time	Departure time on a minute basis.
Vehicle type	Classification of the vehicle in the classes: car, London taxi, motorcycle, pedal cycle, public service vehicle, light goods vehicle, heavy goods vehicle and rigid two axle.
Stopping purpose	Classification of the stopping purpose in the classes: no activity, passenger pick up/drop off, parking, waiting, maintenance, waste collection, parcel pick up/drop off, loading/unloading, unknown.

In collaboration with the City of London, it was decided that the vehicle types that would benefit and be likely to use a booking system were pedal cycles, light goods vehicles, heavy goods vehicles and rigid two axle trucks having stopping purposes of either maintenance, waste collection, parcel pick up/drop off, loading/unloading or unknown. Figure 1 visualises the daily arrivals of the vehicles and stopping purposes interested in the sandboxing project. The arrivals during the two sampling days were more concentrated to the first half of the day, with a peak between 8 am and 12 noon.

Figure 1. Average daily arrival per 15 minutes of pedal cycles, light goods vehicles, heavy goods vehicles and rigid two axle trucks having the stopping purposes of either maintenance, waste collection, parcel pick up/drop off, loading/unloading and unknown.

The duration of the stay for the concerned vehicles and stopping purposes was from a couple of seconds to over 100 min (see Figure 2). The length of stay was similar throughout the day. The data indicated longer stays during the busy period 8 am to 12 noon, but there was no strong indication of this.

Figure 2. Duration of stay in minutes for pedal cycles, light goods vehicles, heavy goods vehicles and rigid two axle trucks having the stopping purposes of either maintenance, waste collection, parcel pick up/drop off, loading/unloading and unknown. Note that this graph illustrates all the events of these concerned vehicle types over the sampling period and not daily.

Model

The aim of the model was to simulate the likelihood of *failed deliveries* to a certain number of designated loading bays. A failed delivery is defined as a transport having no stopping options at the designated loading bays. The failed deliveries can choose to either park in spaces not allowed, resulting in blocking of other traffic, or skip the stop. A delivery stop at a non-permitted space might not have failed in the sense that the vehicle might still stop for the planned purpose, however, in this project it is considered a failed delivery as the stop deviates from the stopping regulations. In the real world, this “failure” corresponds to non-compliant use of the space, which could block the area for other users.

The starting point to estimate the likelihood of failed deliveries was queuing theory and the Erlang B formula, which is commonly used in the telecommunications industry and describes the probability that a customer is blocked upon arrival to a system due to full capacity. The formula presumes that the system has a specific and finite number of identical and parallel service stations. Moreover, the Erlang B formula holds under the premise that if a customer is blocked, the customer will neither be queued nor approach the system’s service again with the same errand, i.e., a blocked customer will vanish from the system. The blocking probability, P , is estimated as:

$$P = B(E, m) = \frac{\frac{E^m}{m!}}{\sum_{i=0}^m \frac{E^i}{i!}}$$

where E is the traffic intensity measured in Erlangs and m the number of service stations. Erlangs are defined as $E = \frac{\lambda}{\mu}$, where λ represents the arrival rate and μ the service rate.

There is resemblance between a parking system with designated loading bays and an Erlang B system. Arriving transports will likely not wait for an available loading bay due to tight schedules, but rather park in illegal spaces or skip the stopping purpose. In comparison to the common telecommunication terminology, a customer in a parking system is a delivery transport and a service station a loading bay. Hence, application of the Erlang B formula will give an estimate of the average probability that an arriving transport will not find any available loading bays.

The Erlang B formula follows the premises that the arrivals are Poisson distributed and that the service times are exponentially distributed. The Poisson distribution describes the probability of a given number of events occurring in a fixed time interval given that the events are independent. Early analysis of the data collected in the City of London indicated that the arrivals at St Mary Axe could be assumed to be Poisson distributed and the stopping times exponentially distributed. Figure 3 visualises the arrival data in comparison with an exponential distribution. There is a resemblance between the data and the exponential distribution which indicates that the length of stops can be assumed to be exponentially distributed, meaning that it is more likely that a delivery transport will stay a short time rather than a longer time.

Figure 3. Comparison of the lengths of stay and an exponential distribution. The graph indicates that it is more likely that a delivery transport would stay a shorter time than a longer time (the dark green scatter). The exponential distribution is estimated for illustration of the distribution’s reasonableness and not fitted to estimate the data.

Figure 4 illustrates the probability mass function of a Poisson distribution. The Poisson distribution describes the probability of a given number of events occurring in a fixed time interval given that the events are independent.

The Poisson distribution is characterised by being centred around a specific value of events, which is the mean. The further away a specific number of events is from the centre value, the more unlikely it is that exactly that number of events will occur. Table 2 demonstrates the number of arrivals per hour on St Mary Axe. The data sampling period of two days is too short to decide with certainty whether the arrivals are Poisson distributed or not. Nevertheless, the number of arrivals during the two days are in most cases close to each other within each hour, i.e., at 6 am the number of arrivals was 9 on the Wednesday and 11 on the Thursday and at 1 pm the number of arrivals were 5 and 4 respectively, indicating that the arrivals could be estimated by a Poisson distribution as the arrivals most frequently will be close to the mean. Since the arrival frequency could be assumed to be Poisson distributed and the stopping times to be exponentially distributed, we were motivated to use the Erlang B formula to estimate the probability of a vehicle finding the loading bays occupied.

Figure 4. Illustration of the probability mass distribution of a Poisson distribution with mean 5.

Table 2. Number of arrivals per hour.

Arrival time	Wed 20 th Nov 2019	Thu 21 st Nov 2019
00:00	1	2
01:00	3	2
02:00	6	5
03:00	8	9
04:00	8	1
05:00	12	8
06:00	9	11
07:00	9	2
08:00	11	8
09:00	12	7
10:00	17	12
11:00	8	6
12:00	10	10
13:00	5	4
14:00	3	3
15:00	1	5
16:00	4	2
17:00	2	0
18:00	2	4
19:00	2	5
20:00	1	2
21:00	1	4
22:00	2	3
23:00	4	5

Assumptions

Models are powerful tools that can be utilised in strategic processes to help planners make decisions. However, models are simplified representations of the real world and are based on assumptions, which should be made transparent.

The parking system model built in this project was constructed to study the peak hour in terms of arrivals; thus, the simulation results represent the worst case and will be an overestimation of the real traffic situation. As visualised in Figure 1, the peak hour for distribution transport arrivals at St Mary Axe is 10 am.

The complex model of a bookable parking system also makes the following assumptions:

- If a transport cannot reserve a loading space at the desired time, the transport will try to book a loading bay at another arbitrary time of the day. Notice that the second choice of arrival time is assumed to have the same characteristics as the first choice.
- Only transports with stopping purpose with a length equal to, or greater than, five minutes will consider using a booking system. It is assumed that the benefit of reserving a bay only exceeds the effort of reserving it when the length of the stay is equal to or greater than five minutes.
- Transports having stops shorter than five minutes will not reserve a loading bay but use the additional non-bookable loading bays.
- Transports reserving a loading bay will book a time slot 30% longer than necessary to be certain they have enough time for their stopping purpose.
- The model is assumed to be a perfect booking system, meaning that there are no inefficiencies in its bookings. If transport A has reserved the bay between 11.20 am and 11.40 am, then the following booking, transport B, has reserved the bay from 11.40 am.
- Not all transports to the street will use the booking system. The share of transports utilising the booking system is presented to the model as a fixed parameter, called the adoption rate.
- The model assumes 100% compliance, meaning that the loading bays will never be occupied by someone who has not booked, and no one will stay longer than scheduled.

As described above, the models representing both alternative 1 (parking system with designated loading spaces where parking is only allowed in the designated loading bays and parking on the street is not regulated by double yellow) and alternative 2 (parking system with bookable loading spaces and additional non-bookable loading bays) assume the arrivals to be Poisson distributed and the stops to be exponentially distributed.

Based on these assumptions two different models were built to explore the two alternatives of designated loading bays and bookable loading bays.

Alternative 1: designated loading bays

The processes in the model for the alternative “designated loading bays” are illustrated in Figure 5. The model was based on the Erlang B formula to estimate the average risk that a transport will not find an available loading bay. Exploration of the stopping activity data on St Mary Axe indicated that the arrivals are assumed to be $Pois(14.5)$, meaning the average arrival per hour is 14.5 delivery transports, and the length of the stays is $Exp(0.08)$, meaning the average stopping time is $\frac{1}{0.08} = 12.5$ minutes. The exponential distribution was estimated such that the expected value of the distribution matched the mean value of the stopping periods given by the data (see Figure 6). The model estimated how many transports could on average not park due to full capacity; these transports were considered failed.

Figure 5. Flow chart of the processes accounted for in model representing the parking system with designated loading bays.

Figure 6. Fitting of length of stay to an exponential distribution.

Alternative 2: bookable loading bays

Alternative 2 considers a parking system with bookable loading bays, which is more complex than alternative 1. In this alternative, a share of the loading bays on the street are bookable, while the remaining bays are non-bookable. The processes accounted for in the model, and the relationship between those processes, are illustrated in Figure 7.

Transports with a stopping purpose that will require more than five minutes will try to reserve a loading bay. However, not all will use the booking system, as there will be some aversion to it. The *adoption rate* describes the share that is willing to use the booking system. If there is no available bookable loading bay in the desired time slot, the transport will try to reserve a loading bay in another arbitrary moment (their second choice). If there are no available loading bay then either, the transport will try to use one of the non-bookable loading bays instead. Similar to alternative 1, both the bookable and non-bookable loading bays are treated as systems where neither retrying nor queueing is allowed. If there is no availability, the transport vanishes from that specific subsystem in the model in accordance with the assumptions on which the Erlang B formula is based.

As with alternative 1, the distributions of the arrivals and lengths of the stays were estimated by exploring the data on the traffic distribution on St Mary Axe. The transports interested in booking a loading bay were assumed to be the ones staying for five minutes or longer. These were estimated to arrive according to $Pois(10.5)$ and have lengths of stay according to $Exp(0.06)$. These distributions were used when modelling an adoption rate of 100%, i.e., where all possible vehicles use the booking system.

The arrivals and stopping times of the transports using the non-bookable bays consisted of the characteristics of three groups of transports:

1. transports having stopping purposes with stays shorter than five minutes;
2. transports that did not want to use the booking system (in case the adoption rate was less than 100 %);
3. transports that did not find an available loading bay.

The last was dependent on the number of bookable loading bays. Thus, the distributions in the subsystem of non-bookable loading bays varied depending on the results from the subsystem of bookable loading bays. Nevertheless, the number of arrivals and the stopping times are considerably lower than in the subsystem composed of bookable loading bays.

Figure 7. Flow chart of the model representing a parking system with bookable loading bays.

Results

Alternative 1: designated loading bays

In alternative 1, all delivery transports were directed to designated loading bays. The loading bays could not be reserved and a transport would find out upon arrival whether a loading bay is available (or not).

Table 3 demonstrates the average risk that a transport will not find an available loading bay upon arrival in the street. The average number of transports not finding an available loading bay in peak hour is calculated by multiplying the risk with the hourly arrival frequency, 14.5. The results can be used by planners to decide how many loading bays are needed to provide a specified *grade of service*. The grade of service represents the tolerated failure probability, if the City of London can tolerate that every fifth transport will not be able to find an available loading bay (meaning at least 20% of the transports are failed deliveries), then St Mary Axe must have at least 3 designated loading bays.

Table 3. Average share and number of transports not finding an available loading bay upon arrival given a specific number of designated loading bays.

Designated loading bays	Average share of transports not finding an available loading bay in peak hour	Average number of transports not finding an available loading bay in peak hour
1	63 %	9.1
2	33 %	4.8
3	14 %	1.9
4	4 %	0.6
5	1 %	0.1
6	0 %	0
7	0 %	0
8	0 %	0
9	0 %	0
10	0 %	0

Alternative 2: bookable loading bays

In alternative 2, a share of the loading bays was designed as bookable. The remainder of the loading bays was non-bookable. The results are presented for two different adoption rates: 50% and 100%. An adoption rate of 100% means that every transport with a stopping purpose over five minutes will use the booking system. The results hold under the assumptions made in the model (see Assumptions).

Each row in Table 4 demonstrates the results of a bookable system with an adoption rate of 100% and a certain number of bookable and non-bookable loading bays. The first two columns of the table illustrate the average risk that transports would not find an available bookable loading bay at either their first or their second choice of arrival time with the given number of bookable loading bays. The transports that are unable to find a bookable loading bay will try to use one of the non-bookable loading bays. The latter two columns illustrate the average risk of transports not able to find an available bookable or non-bookable loading bay. The last two columns illustrate the risk and number of failed deliveries in each booking system. The total number of transports not finding an available loading bay can, on an hourly basis, be calculated by multiplying the total risk (the last column) by the average hourly arrival frequency of 14.5.

Given an adoption rate of 100% and two bookable and two additional non-bookable loading bays, the average risk of failed deliveries in the system would be 5 %, or 0.7 transports. The average risk of not finding an available loading bay decreases as the number of both bookable and non-bookable loading bays increases. If the tolerated grade of service is provided, planners can use simulation results such as these to design suitable parking systems. If the City of London can tolerate a grade of service of 20% on

St Mary Axe (as in the example of alternative 1), then given two bookable loading bays, there must be at least 2 non-bookable loading bays to meet the 20% grade of service.

Table 4. Average share and number of transports not finding an available loading bay upon arrival given a certain number of bookable and non-bookable designated loading bays given an adoption rate of 100 %. The average risk of booking failure represents the transports that wish to reserve a loading bay but fails. The average risk of delivery represents the total risk that an arbitrary transport does not find an available loading bay.

Number of bookable loading bays	Average risk of booking failure	Number of non-bookable loading bays	Average risk of failed delivery
1	70%	1	36%
		2	12%
		3	3%
		4	1%
		5	0%
2	43%	1	21%
		2	5%
		3	1%
		4	0%
		5	0%
3	23%	1	12%
		2	2%
		3	0%
		4	0%
		5	0%
4	10%	1	7%
		2	1%
		3	0%
		4	0%
		5	0%
5	3%	1	5%
		2	1%
		3	0%
		4	0%
		5	0%

As a booking system will likely not have an adoption rate of 100%, it is of great importance to run the model several times using different parameters to span the simulation results over more likely scenarios. Table 4 illustrates the results for a bookable parking system with an adoption rate of 50%. Compared with a system with an adoption rate of 100% (see Table 4), the risk of failed deliveries decreases only minimally for systems with few (in this case, one) bookable loading bays. This is expected as the demand for the bookable loading bays will decrease if fewer are willing to use the booking system and instead

use the non-bookable loading bays. The non-bookable loading bays on St Mary Axe have less occupancy due to fewer arrivals and shorter stays compared to the bookable loading bays, even when a share of the transports having a longer stay is interested in the non-bookable loading bays.

However, if the street has more than one bookable loading bay, the risk of failed deliveries is more likely than in the scenario with an adoption rate of 100%. The reason for this is that the risk of failed deliveries stabilises for two or more bookable loading bays given an adoption rate of 50%. With two or more loading bays, there is, essentially, enough capacity to handle all transports interested in booking, meaning there is almost no risk for these transports of not finding an available loading bay. This means that there will be no additional transports in the non-bookable subsystem coming from the bookable subsystem. This will result in stabilised arrival and service time distributions and a stabilised result. Hence, if the parking system has a higher number of bookable loading bays, a good enough adoption rate is vital for a system to avoid the risk of full capacity in the system.

Table 4. Average share and number of transports not finding an available loading bay upon arrival given a certain number of bookable and non-bookable designated loading bays given an adoption rate of 50 %. The average risk of booking failure represents the transports that wish to reserve a loading bay but fails. The average risk of delivery represents the total risk that an arbitrary transport does not find an available loading bay.

Number of bookable loading bays	Average risk of booking failure	Number of non-bookable loading bays	Average risk of failed delivery
1	51%	1	34%
		2	10%
		3	2%
		4	0%
		5	0%
2	18%	1	25%
		2	6%
		3	1%
		4	0%
		5	0%
3	4%	1	21%
		2	5%
		3	1%
		4	0%
		5	0%
4	1%	1	20%
		2	4%
		3	1%
		4	0%
		5	0%
5	0%	1	20%
		2	4%
		3	1%
		4	0%
		5	0%

Comparison between Alternative 1 and Alternative 2

When deciding whether a street should have a bookable parking system or just a parking system composed of designated loading bays, it is important to analyse the different behaviours of the alternatives. For example, if there were space for four loading bays on St Mary Axe, these four loading bays could be combined between bookable and non-bookable loading bays in four different combinations. Table 5. Given that four loading bays are available on St Mary Axe, these are the total average risks of failed deliveries based on the different design options between bookable and non-bookable loading bays.

Table 6 provides a comparison of these different combinations and their respective risk of failed delivery. Based on the simulation results, the best combination is one bookable loading bay together with three non-bookable loading bays. For those combinations, the risks for failed deliveries are 3% and 2 % with adoption rates of 100 % and 50 %, respectively. Such an analysis reveals that it is better to have one bookable loading bay than four non-bookable loading bays, however, four non-bookable loading bays are better than to have three bookable loading bays together with one non-bookable loading bay.

Table 5. Given that four loading bays are available on St Mary Axe, these are the total average risks of failed deliveries based on the different design options between bookable and non-bookable loading bays.

Number of bookable loading bays	Number of non-bookable loading bays	Alternative 1: designated loading bays	Alternative 2: bookable loading bays with an adoption rate of 100 %	Alternative 2: bookable loading bays with an adoption rate of 50 %
3	1	-	12%	21%
2	2	-	5%	6%
1	3	-	3%	2%
0	4	4%	-	-

Evaluation

This section aims to evaluate the results in broader perspectives. Constraints in the procedures of the models will be emphasised and the strengths and weaknesses of bookable parking systems in the real world will be discussed.

The main constrain of the model representing a bookable system is that it assumes a perfect booking system. The mathematical principles on which the model is based represent an average snapshot of the system and do not specifically consider earlier and future events. A booking system, however, is dependent on earlier and future events as bookings stretch over a time interval. As with many other queuing models, the booking process in the model handles the system's service as *first come, first served*, meaning that the customers of the system will be able to reserve a time slot in the order of their arrivals to the system, which is an accurate representation of an actual booking system. Transport A will have more time slots to select from if it reserves a loading bay before transport B does. As described in the

Background, a booking system has the inherent challenge of inefficiency in terms of suboptimal use. The inefficiency challenge is visualised in Figure 8. But since the principles the model is based upon represent an average snapshot, these event-dependent booking principles are not accounted for in the model. The

model's assumption of the average snapshot results in a perfect booking system that does not account for any of the described inefficiency challenges, meaning the results are overestimated.

Figure 8. Illustration of the inefficiency inherent in the model representing bookable loading bays. The letters represent different transports arriving to system. They arrive in alphabetical order, A, B, C. The next arriving transport, D, will not be able to reserve a time if his/her stopping time is greater than the time available. The pie visualises a full hour.

As mentioned, models are merely simplified representations of the real world. The real world is almost always more complex and more unpredictable than assumptions made in a model can allow for. Users of the model should be well acquainted with the premises of the results when drawing conclusions from them. The model holds under the assumption that transports having stopping purposes for five minutes or longer will be interested in booking a loading bay. In the real world, some transports having shorter stays than five minutes might be interested in reserving a loading bay, as well as vice versa, transports having longer stays than five minutes might not be interested in reserving a loading bay. The interest in reserving a loading bay depends, most certainly, on several aspects, i.e.:

- How time dependent the delivery is.
- Length of the stopping purpose.
- Risk of getting penalized for the violating the regulations, i.e., by getting a parking ticket.
- Size of the punishment, i.e., the size of the parking ticket.

Furthermore, the interest will probably not be dependent on one aspect alone, but a combination of several of them. It is important that the city implementing a bookable parking system discuss the types of vehicle types and stopping purposes they want to regulate with the specific parking system. If the delivery traffic is composed of many shorter stays, a bookable parking system might not be the best alternative as it is more difficult to ensure that the transport arrives at the loading bay at the reserved time. Moreover, it could be difficult to motivate transports with shorter stays to use the booking system as they might perceive the cost of booking greater than the benefits. Future work on bookable parking system could investigate the perceived costs and benefits and what environments encourage deliveries to utilise booking systems.

Furthermore, the models do not specifically account for a loading bay's attractiveness in relation to the location of the stopping purpose. It is likely that a loading bay will be less attractive if there is longer distance between the loading bay and the delivery location. The adoption rate consider this aspect to a certain extent by varying transports' willingness to utilise the booking system. However, to be able to analyse the effects of the locations of loading bays on the street, the location must be a variable in the model.

Regardless of the model's constraints with handling interval dependent events, this inefficiency will also be one of the greatest challenges in a real case. Planners designing a bookable parking system must discuss and analyse the best design of the specific street's needs. One question to discussion is how the system minimises the inherent inefficiency in booking systems. It should be well motivated why there should be bookable parking system if the risk of failed delivery is greater with than without a bookable parking system. Such motives could be ensuring availability for time dependent deliveries or transports having stopping purposes important to the society that would not have a good enough success rate otherwise. Another question to discuss is how the system should ensure compliance. Ensuring compliance is a complex challenge and could on a higher level be described as being composed of law enforcement measures together with incentives of utilising the booking system. As seen in the results, the adaption rate influences the risk of failure, and the system must, in many cases, be designed to motivate potential users to use it. The question of compliance is too complex to analyse and consider in this report, nevertheless, if implementing a bookable parking system, questions such as compliance and inefficiency should be addressed by the planners.

Summary and conclusions

This sandboxing project has emphasised the opportunities of analysing the effects of different kinds of parking systems by models build upon general mathematical formulas in order to analyse these questions on a more general level. The work done in this project finds that there is potential in using this approach. However, the model developed in this project does not account for all behaviours linked to booking and needs to be developed further in coming projects to represent a more virtual environment better reflective of reality. The model simulates the average risk that an arbitrary transport will not find an available loading bay, however, note that there are situations of expectational circumstances not well represented by the average, such as occasional traffic peaks greater than anticipated.

If a city decides to implement bookable loading bays, the experience gained in this project suggests that the number of bookable and non-bookable loading bays should be carefully analysed. Furthermore, the inherent inefficiency challenges in booking systems should be well analysed and action plans created to handle these challenges.